

NEW METHODS TO TEACHING THE SCOTTISH LITERATURE AND POEMS OF ROBERT BURNS

Yakubova Makhbubakhon Mamatismailovna,
ASIFL, teacher

Annotation. This article discusses the importance of studying both national and world literature in language education. It explains how literature helps students develop the four basic language skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. The article highlights the role of literary texts, especially poetry, in improving fluency, vocabulary, creativity, and communication abilities. Special attention is given to the teaching of poetry through interactive classroom activities based on the works of Robert Burns, one of the most famous representatives of Scottish literature. The article also provides practical recommendations for literature teachers, including reading activities, poetry recitation, group performances, and fluency-building exercises. Overall, the article emphasizes that literature is an effective educational tool that develops students' imagination, critical thinking, and language competence.

Key Words: Scottish Literature, Robert Burns, Poetry, Reading Fluency, Literary Texts, Teaching Literature, Classroom Activities

We should learn not only our Uzbek national literature but also, we should learn World Literature too. When the man knows all about World Literature, then he can become a literary educated person. We should learn the following things to know all about Word literature or foreign literature: First of all, we should know what the literature is itself and World literature. And then we must learn the history of the literature, after the history of literature we learn periods in it. Every period of literature plays a great role in the teaching literature. We should carefully explain periods and representatives in them. We know that a lot of great writers created wonderful novels, stories, plays and poems in English literature. Their works kept till nowadays and everybody can learn them if they wanted from textbooks or internet.

Literature plays an important role in teaching four basic language skills like reading, writing, listening and speaking. However, when using literature in the language classroom, skills should never be taught in isolation but in an integrated way. Teachers should try to teach basic language skills as an integral part of oral and written language use, as part of the means for creating both referential and interactional meaning, not merely as an aspect of the oral and written production of words, phrases and sentences.

Literary texts are incomparable sources for all the types of learning skills, reading, writing, listening and even speaking. A question may arise in this point "What can be done in order to bring literary texts to the class of listening and speaking?" in listening lessons we may use recordings of different stories. In order to widen its benefit for language learners we can use different types of questions and activities, even play games. For example:

1. What sort of person do you think the character in this poem is? Name the three characteristics you find most obvious, and say in each case what words and phrases from the poem make you feel as you do?

2. What particular feeling does this poem waken in you? Name the emotion, and try to say what it was in the story that made you feel this way?

We try to give some recommendations to the literature teachers:

Choose the type of literature you wish to teach. In many cases, this should be literature appropriate to the children's age level, but you can find clever ways to include more sophisticated works if you wish. Stories of Greek myths aimed at younger audiences are a good place to start. Try to look for stories that contain strong hooks for kids: a good adventure, for instance, or fairy tales written for their age group.

Read the book aloud in the classroom, either by reading it yourself or having different children take turns reading passages. Older kids also may benefit from periods of silent reading in which they cover a given book on their own. At the end of each reading session, ask the children what they thought of the passage, how they felt the hero acted and what they might do if they were in the same place.

Give periodic quizzes after each reading session to test for comprehension and vocabulary. You may wish to assign writing lessons, too, asking the children to write short reviews or thoughts on the piece they have just read.

Connect the literature to the children's own lives. One of the biggest difficulties in teaching English literature to kids is showing them how the stories are pertinent to their world. Ask them if they see any traits in the heroes that they themselves share, or have them compare some part of the story to things they may have seen or done in their own lives.

Consider putting on a play based on the literature you are reading. It can be as simple or as elaborate as you like and your resources allow. By role-playing the characters in the story, your students can develop a greater affinity for them and further understand how the literature connects to their own lives.

Asking questions can also be helpful while reading a story and other forms of literature. This might be done in the following way: before reading a passage students should be asked some questions such as, "What is the story about? When the event happened? What happens to the hero? Why...? How many...?" etc. This helps the learners to arise their consciousness on reading and builds their motivation of reading.

"The Great Poetry Race" became popular and motivational among students and increased student's participation from kindergarten to high school. The teacher identified substantial literacy growth in the students who participated. This study proved that students who read a poem multiple times, had more opportunities to improve reading abilities and in return succeeded academically.

In life, communication is essential. Communication is art. Poetry is art. Poetry promotes literacy, builds fluency, and fosters positive language and experience connections.

Poetry is universal. Poetry opens venues for a robust English Language Arts curriculum. Poetry is accessible for all students in the classroom. Because poetry defies rules, poetry can be easily scaffolded and students can find ways of expressing themselves.

Poetry can enrich the reader by offering a new way to view everyday experiences. Poetry allows students to play with language. When poetry read aloud occurs, it is rhythmical and musical. Poetry allows students to paint sketches of their lives, using metaphors, imagery, and

symbolic language to describe experiences. When students read poetry, they have the opportunity to travel around the world with their imaginations.

Also, poetry is short, it does not need to be analyzed, and it does not need to be deconstructed. Teachers need to find the poems of Robert Burns that wake up students' interests, that make them feel as if they've submerged themselves in an imaginative world full of rich language.

The simplest reason reading fluency is important is because without fluency, reading is not enjoyable. When a fluent reader reads with accuracy, expression, and voice, reading is more enjoyable, rewarding, and effortless. As a student becomes a fluent reader, this fluency positively influences what the student will choose to read independently. Fluent readers will pick up a book and read on their own, even when it is not assigned for class.

When reading words becomes automatic, students can then simultaneously engage in processing the meaning of the words being read. Fluent reading leads to more success with writing, better vocabulary skills, and a greater understanding of what is being read.

Objective: To have the students read the poem multiple times, build fluency, to identify rhyming and high frequency words.

Materials: Poem, chart paper, sentence strips, and a pencil.

Procedure: Teacher and students select the poem of Robert Burns as a whole group.

Teacher writes the poem of Robert Burns on chart paper and as a whole class, circles the rhyming words. Then, reads the poem again and highlights the high frequency words.

Students practice the poem of Robert Burns throughout the week in pairs, choral reading, repeated reading, at home, and with the teacher. Each student may write one of the poem sentences on sentence strips to practice.

Three voluntary students perform the poem to the class and family members. The class completes secret ballots to select the week's Fluency Idol. All the participants receive a special Fluency Idol certificate for their efforts.

Students can memorize and act out the poem of Robert Burns like a reader's theater with inflections. ELs or SNs: Adapt this activity using pictures and allow multiple opportunities to practice, and permit various repetitions.

With parent permission, the teacher will record the performance and make a CD for the class to listen to it. Students may re-read the poem multiple times to memorize and perform the poem for a school assembly. As students re-read the poem daily to can memorize and act it out the poem like a reader's theater with inflections; also, students can make a video and uploaded to the school website.

Name of Activity: Cumulative Build-Up Poem Presentation

Objective: To have a student voice read the first line, then two more join in on the second line, and then three more join in on the third line, gradually building to a crescendo until the entire class says the last line to build fluency.

Material: Poem and highlighters.

Procedure:

- On Monday, the teacher and students select the poem of Robert Burns they will perform on Friday. Next, the students select the lines they are responsible for and highlight it.

- On Tuesday, the students re-read the poem and identify vocabulary words and discuss them for clarification.

- On Wednesday, the students practice reading the poem to the other grade level classmates.

- On Thursday, the students practice reading the poem in the staff room.

- Throughout the week, students practice their poems at school during their reading time and at home with their family members.

- On Friday, students will voluntarily perform the poem to the class after the flag salute and the morning announcements.

Students can choose two lines from the poem. Students can highlight the lines they need to memorize.

Students can memorize their lines. Then, students can recite the poem to a first-grade classroom.

ELs or SNs: Adapt this activity using one line, write the poem line on a sentence strip, discuss any vocabulary or unknown word using picture cards, use tape recorder to record their voices for multiple opportunities to practice, and permit various repetitions, and time to performance.

Name of Activity: From a Simultaneous Recitation to a Musical Round

Poems to be used: Appropriate for 5th and 6th Grade.

Objective: To have each group of students recite the poem of Robert Burns to a musical round multiple times to build fluency.

Material: Poem and chart paper

Procedure:

- On Monday, the teacher divides the entire class into groups (A, B, C, D) four students per group. Then the teacher and students select the poem of Robert Burns they will perform on Friday.

- Next, the teacher explains how the poem is going to be read: Group A begins the poem and recites it all the way through. When Group A begins the third line, then Group B starts the first line, later when group B begins the third line, then Group C starts the first line. Finally, Group D can be added as Group C begins the third line.

- On Tuesday, the teacher may record the students on an iPad as they read the poem simultaneously to see and hear them for improvement.

- Throughout the week, students practice their poems at school during their fluency time.

On Friday, students may perform the poem voluntarily to another class.

The teacher records the students' presentation and email a copy to each of their parents.

Answer the following questions which given from text or information you have learnt at the lesson

- 1) What do you know about English literature?
- 2) What kind of literary trends do you know?
- 3) What is Scottish literature?
- 4) Can you tell the name of the famous Scottish writers and poets?
- 5) Where and when was born Robert Burns?
- 6) What kind of literary trend does he belong?
- 7) What kind of works did he create?
- 8) What do you know about the poems "A Red, Red Rose" and "My Heart's in the Highlands"?
- 9) What is the writing style of Robert Burns?
- 10) What is the theme of Robert Burns?

Read and discuss:

- 1) Robert Burns' life story
- 2) The poem "A Red, Red Rose"
- 3) The poem "[To a Louse](#)"

Describe the nature by own words after reading the poem "My Heart's in the Highlands".

Recite some poems of Robert Burns.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Bakoeva M., Muratova E., Ochilova M. "English literature" Tashkent 2006
2. Hogg, PS Robert Burns. The Patriot Bard. Edinburgh: Mainstream Publishing. p. 321. 2008.
3. John Peck, Martin Coyle. A brief history of English literature. Palgrave, 2002.
4. Leask, Nigel "Burns and the Poetics of Abolition". In Carruthers, Gerard. Edinburgh Companion to Robert Burns. Edinburgh University Press. p. 51. 2009.
5. Liliana Sikorska. An outline history of English literature. p. 529, 2003
6. Robert Burns "[Scotland's National Bard](#)". Scottish Executive. 2009.
7. Robert Burns: "[Poetry – Poems – Poets](#)." Retrieved on 24 September 2010
8. Thornley G.C. An outline of English literature. Longman, 2003.
9. <https://my.gov.uz>
10. <http://en.wikipedia.org>
11. <http://www.online-literature.com>

